

Information Security: Steganography & Cryptography

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Abstract—With the progression in technology, a large number of applications make use of the Internet. With such a system in place, the dependence on digital interaction has grown up tremendously. In this process, large quantity of data is traded over a network and such data is vulnerable to unauthorized access and manipulation. Therefore, in order to protect the data, to provide security and protection, two methods known as Steganography and Cryptography are used. In steganography, data is implanted in a multimedia file and transmitted over the network. While in cryptography, data is transmitted by encryption or in other words, by transforming it into a different format.

Index Terms—Steganography, Cryptography, Steganalysis, Cryptanalysis, Cryptocurrencies.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the evolution of internet, private and personal communication over the web has become one of the widely used applications of Information technology and communication. This brings forth the idea of data security as there is an exchange of data in the process. Over the years, many techniques have been established to encrypt and decrypt data to ensure confidentiality, one among them being Cryptography. However, in the recent years, keeping the message secret is considered insufficient which gives rise to the concept of keeping the presence of message secret. This is implemented by a technique called Steganography.

II. STEGANOGRAPHY AND CRYPTOGRAPHY

Steganography [1] is the art and science of hiding the fact that communication is taking place. Originating from a Greek word “*stegos*” meaning “*roof or covered*” and “*graphia*” meaning “*writing*”. So, it literally means *covered writing*. The main objective of steganography is to communicate securely in a completely imperceptible manner and to avoid drawing suspicion to the transmission of a hidden data [2]. In *Histories* the Greek historian Herodotus writes about a Greek in the Persian Court who sent a warning of approaching invasion by Xerxes by writing a message on a wooden pallet and then covering it in wax. The messenger was able to successfully smuggle the “blank” tablet to Sparta [3].

With the evolving technology, steganographic technique has also evolved. *Invisible inks* [3] created from organic materials such as milk, juices or urine became one of the weapons of steganographic techniques. The hidden writing is visible when

heat is applied to the document.

Below figure shows four key file formats that are primarily used for steganography [5].

Figure 1: Categories of steganography

In [4] a steganographic approach is used that uses sensitivity of human vision to hide secret bits. Firstly, the secret data is transformed into series of symbols to be rooted in a notation system with multiple bases. The degree of local variation of the pixel magnitude of the image determines the particular bases that are used.

Cryptography is the science of secret writing. Encryption is the process where a plaintext is converted to some other form (known as ciphertext); whereas the reverse process is called decryption which gives back the plaintext from ciphertext. Both encryption and decryption are controlled by a cryptographic key.

III. STEGANALYSIS AND CRYPTANALYSIS

In simple words, steganalysis is defined as the discovery of steganography by any third party. With the limitations of human perception, a stego-image can be created by carefully choosing a suitable cover image and stego-tool. [3].

Nevertheless [3], every tool leaves an electronic fingerprint or signature in the formed file that can make an observer aware of the existence of any concealed messages. First step of steganalysis is to discover the hidden message and is also considered an attack on the hidden information. There are different forms of attack depending on what type of information is present in front of the steganalyst (one who does steganalysis).

Steganographic tools can however leave certain detectable traces in the newly formed file though they alter only the least-significant image component. As a result, successful attack can still take place from the traces left behind [6].

Detection of hidden data/information is the primary objective of attacks against steganography, but it is also possible in some cases to extract and/or destroy the data. Here,

it is referred to as the presence of hidden data/information in a given image. In general, steganalysis involves two major types of techniques: Statistical Analysis and Visual Analysis.

Statistical Analysis is more powerful as it can reveal an image's statistical behaviour caused due to steganographic embedding. Due to a range of approaches present to embed the image, each approach modifies the image in a different way. The statistical analysis methods are more effective than the nominally universal methods to detect the embedded data.[7].

Visual Analysis on the other hand completely relies on inspection by naked eyes or with a computer assistance to reveal the presence of any secret communication. With computer assistance an image can be decomposed into bit-planes. To detect the existence of secret information/data there has to be any unexpected display of the LSB-plane. It is very effective when secret information is inserted in areas with pixel values nearer saturation [7].

Table 1 below contains few of the most popular steganalytic methods [7].

Steganalytic Methods	Description	Targeted Steganographic Techniques
RS steganalysis	Sensitivity of dual statistics based on spatial correlation of pixels to LSB randomization due to steganographic embedding is used in analysis.	Various LSB modification techniques
PoV-based Chi-square test	A Chi-square test checks whether the occurrence of each pair of values tends to become equal, indicating some data is embedded.	Steganography based on swapping pairs of values of pixel gray levels, colors, or DCT coefficients
Palette checking	Peculiarity in palette ordering is a clear sign of systematic modification.	Steganography in palette images
RQP method	Method based on analyzing the increased number of close-color pairs caused by embedding.	LSB embedding in true-color images
Check JPEG compatibility	Method detects unusual departure from the JPEG signature inherent in images initially stored in JPEG format.	Space-domain steganography using images initially stored in the JPEG format
Histogram analysis	Method reveals discreteness or periodicity in particular coefficients due to quantization-related modification.	QIM or other quantization-related embedding methods
Universal blind detection	Statistical quantities constructed using high-order statistics, and a detection model established with the threshold obtained in a training process.	Various steganographic techniques

Table 1

Cryptanalysis [8] refers to the inverse engineering of cryptography. Also refers to the attack that do not attack the weakness in the algorithm itself but instead finds the weakness of their implementation. It aims to understand how cryptography works and find the techniques to defeat or weaken them even when the cryptographic key is not known to the attacker. The techniques and methods of cryptanalysis has also evolved through the history of cryptography.

Brute force attack or *Exhaustive key search attack* can be used where attacker can try all possible keys to decrypt the ciphertext until a correct key is matched and it is applicable to all the algorithms. The attacker needs to try on average 2^{k-1} keys if the key size is k bits [12].

Side Channel Analysis attack [12] targets the physical observable vulnerabilities such as heat indulgence, power, microprocessor time required for execution, etc. These attacks can be avoided by adding some noise, buffered output sequence, deliberate reduction in signal size.

Algebraic attack models a cryptographic system with respect to algebraic equations. Firstly, a set of equations is required to find that will relate the output stream and initial state, after this the keystream bits are noted, and values are

substituted into the equation [12]. At last, the equations are solved to get the initial state and the secret key is derived.

Divide and Conquer attack divides the cipher into several subcomponents and at each stage few key bits are determined [12].

IV. CRYPTOGRAPHY FOR SECRECY?

Cryptography mainly constitutes of plain text and cipher text. The original data/information is termed as plain text and the encrypted version of the data is termed as cipher text. Now, the cipher text can in turn be decrypted to get the original data.

Cryptography can be broadly classified into – *Symmetric Key Cryptography* and *Asymmetric Key Cryptography*.

A. Symmetric Key Cryptography

Symmetric key cryptography also referred to as secret-key or shared key cryptography. In this sort of cryptography, the sender and receiver share a common key for both encryption and decryption of data/message [10]. The common key is self-certified as they follow self-certification method. The common key must be shared through secret communication. Any attacker can encrypt the data if the key is compromised or retrieved from the secret communication flow. This type of cryptographic technique provides faster service without using many resources [10]. AES, DES, 3DES, Blowfish algorithms have been developed so far to describe symmetric key cryptography.

Figure. 2. Symmetric key cryptography

B. Asymmetric Key Cryptography

Asymmetric key cryptography also called as public key cryptography. Here the concept of self-certification is not present like in symmetric key cryptography. In this mechanism the sender uses the public key provided by the receiver to encrypt the data/message and the receiver uses his own private key to decrypt the data/message. Since the concept of self-certification is not present here, digital signatures are used to certify the keys instead [10]. This

procedure provides better security and authentication as privacy is kept intact however attacks can still occur if vulnerabilities are still present. RSA, Diffie-Hellman, ECC and Digital Signature Algorithm are few algorithms to implement asymmetric key cryptography.

Figure. 3. Asymmetric key cryptography

V. REAL WORLD APPLICATION

A possible way to send news, data and information without being censored can be termed as Steganography. It tries to reduce the fear of interception of information/data and tracing back to the source. On the other hand, what cryptography does is hide the content of the message. This results in suspicion that the encrypted data package contains information which is valuable. Steganography adds one more step to cryptography process i.e., it makes the ciphertext/encrypted data invisible to unauthorized users. So, it is basically cryptography and an additional property. The human brain and eye is incapable of seeing more than a thousand frames per second. When a video runs at say four thousand frames per second and every third frame of it is a hidden image, then the hidden image will not be visible to any human sight. Any modern steganographic technique can conceal images within a video and it can skip any human attention. However, if the video is paused in certain unlucky time frame it would reveal the hidden images.

There are various tools or platforms that can be used to achieve steganography to hide files inside other files on a computer, like:

- Xiao Steganography,
- SSuite Picsel,
- Steghide,
- OpenPuff

A. Key Distribution

One of the major problems in implementing cryptography is

to distribute the keys between sender and receiver of the information, data or message and not to any third party or attacker. Obviously, the best way to keep the keys secret is to use cryptography. *Data Encrypting Keys* are the keys used to encrypt and decrypt data. Other type of keys called *key encrypting keys* are used to encrypt such *data encrypting keys* so that they can be transmitted and kept in computer systems for use. Now if an attacker gets hold of any *data encrypting key* then he/she can have access to the data/information protected by that specific key. However, if any *key encrypting key* comes is made available to the attacker, he/she can exploit all *data encrypting keys* protected by that and which in turn will allow access to the data/information protected by that key. So, it is very important to protect the keys also the distribution needs to be taken place carefully.

B. Identification and authentication

Authentication can be termed as the process of proving and verifying certain information. There are scenarios where one may want to authenticate a document origin, identity if any sender, the date and time any document was created or signed, etc. Many of these could be authenticated and verified by a cryptographic process called digital signature. The signer's private key and the document together constitutes the digital signature of the document. It is created through the application of hash function along with an algorithm that creates encrypted character comprising of the private key and specific information about the document.

There are several other methods of authentication and identification such as biometric authentication, password base authentication, multifactor authentication, etc.

C. Cryptocurrencies

Cryptocurrency is a recent phenomenon that is receiving significant attention. Cryptography plays a crucial role in generating and distributing the currency units [11]. A system that allows one to one digital exchange currency units. The involved process requires distributed verification of the required transaction excluding any central authority. Mining is the verification process that can confirm the transaction amount, whether any payer owns the currency they want to spend while it is ensured that the currency units are not spent twice [11]. Base on any particular requirements a variety of mining technologies can be used by cryptocurrencies.

Cryptocurrencies functionally works in the following ways [11]:

- There is a wallet for each user with a generated address and the address acts as a *public key* [11].
- To prove ownership/authenticity and sign any transaction, the wallet also contains a *private key* [11].
- The sender sends money to the receiver's address and signs the money with sender's private key.
- These transactions are then verified by mining [11].

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